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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF CHEWABLE TABLET OF BENZOCAIN BY DIFFERENT BINDER CONCENTRATION

Mr. Sonawane M.P.¹, Miss Gangurde R. R.¹, Miss Bagul P.K.¹, Mrs. Sonawane B. M.²

¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy. Manur, Kalwan.

²Department of Pharmacognosy, Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy. Manur, Kalwan.

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ABSTRACT

Benzocain is chemically described as ethyl ester of para amino benzoic acid having local anaesthetic activity. It is readily absorbed from mucous membrane and poorly absorption through the skin. In water and dilute acid it is sparingly soluble and in chloroform and ethanol it is very soluble. Generally its administration by oral route. In case of throat disorders the patients who cannot swallow tablets hence benzocain chewable tablets helps to improve patient compliance. Chewable tablets were prepared with PVP k30 binder with different concentration 20 %, 30% and 40 % Tablet prepared by wet granulation method were performed and evaluation is done for different parameters such as weight variation, Hardness, percent comprasability, Tapped density, friability, Content uniformity, Disintegration etc. All parameters were found within specifications of 30 % binder concentration. Assay value limit were found within limit 95% to 110%.

Corresponding author

Mr. Sonawane Mitesh Popatrao

Loknete Dr. J. D. Pawar College of Pharmacy,
Manur, Kalwan Dist. Nashik,
Maharashtra (423501).
sonawanemitesh1919@gmail.com
9604300101

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INTRODUCTION

Benzocaine is chemically described as para amino benzoate. Benzocaine is a ethyl ester of para amino benzoic acid does not containing tertiary amine with local anaesthetic activity. It is readily absorbed from mucous membrane and poorly absorption through skin. Benzocaine metabolize by plasma cholinesterase and lesser to externally by hepatic cholinesterase. It has duration of action 15 to 30 minutes.

In water n dilute acid it is sparingly soluble and in chloroform and ethanol it is very soluble. The pKa of the aromatic amine is 3.5. Oral route of administration is most common and easiest way to administer a drug. But childrens are not learned to swallow tablets and also in case of gediatics who can not swallow tablets due throat disorders. Hence benzocaine chewable tablets are helpful to improve the compliance in gediatics and childrens. Chewable tablets are chewed in between the teeth before ingestion. These tablets are given to the patients who cannot swallow the tablet due to throat problems. The benzocaine chewable tablets having advantages include precise dosing, palatability, stability, portability and ease of transport. It is well- tolerated,safe alternative to traditional and conventional drug formulations and offer significant advantages in pediatrics with two years age and above. In present formulation of benzocaine chewable tablets were prepared by wet granulation method by using different binder concentration and all three batches were evaluated. The main aim of the present paper was to formulate and evaluate benzocaine chewable tablet by using different binder concentration.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

The benzocaine drug sample was praped in laboratory. All other ingredients viz. sucrose, mannitol, PVP K30, Talc etc used were of pharmaceutical grade.

Method

Weigh all ingredients acurately with required quantity and passed through sieve mesh no 80. PVP K30 solution of concentration 20%, 30% and 40% were by using alcohol as a solvent and other ingredients are mixed and wet granulation method was followed as below

Wet granulation method:-

For the preparation binder solution of PVP K30 20 %, 30% and 40% with quantity 5 ml ethanol in beaker and stirred with glass rod to form homogeneous solution. The next ingredient mannitol were passed through mesh 30. Sucrose were passed through sieve no. 40 Talc and benzocaine were passed through sieve no. 100. Benzocaine, sucrose, mannitoland half quantity of talc was taken in mortar and dropwise addition of PVP K30 20% solutuion were added and mixed well to form damp mass, sieve no. 60 was use to passed damped mass for prepration of granules. Granules were dried and remaning quantity of talc were added. After compete drying granules .The flow properties of granules were found to be as per specifications .The batch of 30 tablets were prepared with thhe help of evaluated granules,each tablet weight of 260 mg .

Manufacturing formula for tablets of different binder concentration as given in table .

Table 1 :manufacturing formula for chewable tablet.

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity (1 tab)	Quantity (40 tab)
1	Benzocaine	15mg	0.6 gm
2	Sucrose	20mg	0.8gm
3	Mannitol	180mg	7.2gm
4	PVP K30	q.s	q.s
5	Talc	25mg	1gm

Evaluation of Granules:**Bulk Density:**

Bulk density was measured by following method. Pour the granule sample into 100ml graduated measuring cylinder at 45° angle and measure the volume filled with granules material. Table 2 shows the variation in bulk density of benzocaine tablet with different binder concentration.

Tapped Density:

Tapped density was measured by following method. Granules sample was added into 100ml graduated measuring cylinder, containing sample was mechanically tapped 1500 times and measured the final volume and calculated by using formula as shown in table 2.

Percent compressibility :

The percent compressibility of benzocaine was calculated by using following formula-

$$\text{Percent compressibility (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{tapped density} - \text{bulk density}}{\text{tapped density}} \right] \times 100$$

Hausner Ratio:

The Hausner ratio of Benzocaine tablet was calculated by using following formula-

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \frac{\text{Taped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

less than 1.25 value indicates good flow,
while greater than 1.25 indicates poor flow

Angle of repose :

To measure angle of repose, a powdered sample was poured from funnel attached to stand. Distance from surface is 2 cm. The height of hill was measured with scale and circle was drawn around the powder hill. Diameter was measured on graph paper. The angle of repose was determined by using following formula.

$$\text{Angle of repose} = \tan \theta = \frac{2 \text{ height}}{\text{diameter}}$$

Evaluation of Tablets:**General appearance:**

The identity of any tablet is essential for patient compliance and acceptance and it mainly depends upon general appearance of tablets, elegance. The general appearance of any tablet mainly depends upon on tablet size, colour of tablet, shape of tablet presence and absence of odour, surface texture, taste and consistency. Hence presence of cracks depression, uniformity of colour, pinholes and polish of tablet surface were checked.

Dimensions:

The determination of shape and dimensions of compressed benzocaine chewable tablets were by using the of tooling technology during the compression process. At the constant compressive load, tablet thickness depends on change in die fill, flow properties and size distribution and tablet weight and also dimensions varies with change in compression load. Digital vernier caliper is used for measurement of thickness and diameter of tablet. Tablet thickness should be controlled within a $\pm 5\%$ variation of standard value.

Weight variation test:

Tablet designed to contain a specific amount of drug in a specific amount of tablet formula. Weight variation test were performed by weighing 10 tablets individually, individual tablet weight is compared with average tablet weight. 15% acceptance value is allowed for first 10 dosage unit. If the acceptance value is greater than 15%, test next 20 units and calculate acceptance value. The requirements are met if final acceptance value of the 30 dosage units is less than or equal to 15%, and no individual content of any dosage unit is less than nor more than 25%. The percent deviation of weight of tablet was determined by using following formula:

$$\text{Percentage deviation} = \left[\frac{\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight}}{\text{Average weight}} \right] \times 100.$$

Hardness Test:

Adequate tablet hardness and resistance to powdering and friability are necessary to requisites for consumer acceptance. Tablet hardness determined by using following method, tablet were placed between two anvils, force is applied to anvils and the crushing strength that just causes the tablet to break was recorded. Test was done using Monsanto tester (Model no-NK200). The average of six determinations was determined and reported for determination of hardness factor. The hardness was measured in kilograms per centimetre square.

Friability Test:

Friability is determine to check whether the loss of weight of tablet in container or package , due to removal of fine particals from the surface of tablets these can also add to tablet's weight variation or content uniformity problems. The present tablet formulation was evaluated for the friability test with the help of Roche type friabilator. The tablet weighings upto 6 grams is consider as initial weight and are introduced into friability apparatus rotating 100 revolutions. The tablets are then dusted and reweight.The friability was calculated with the help of following formula in triplets.

$$\text{Friability} = [\text{initial weight}- \text{final weight} / \text{initial weight}]\times 100$$

Disintegration Time:

Disintegration time indicates that time required for availability of maximum concentration of medicament it is important for breakdown of tablets into granules or smaller particles. The disintegration test was performed at temperature $37\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ by using 6 tablets. disintegration of tablet were evaluated with specification as shown in observation table.

Dissolution:

The rate of dissolution may thus be directly related to the efficacy of tablet product, as well as to bioavailability differences between formulations. Dissolution measurements were carried out in a USP Dissolution test apparatus type-2. The dissolution medium for benzocaine chewable tablet 0.1 N HCL having pH 1.2 were used the tablet were placed in apparatus and paddle is rotated 50rpm. dissolution volume of 900ml and its temperature is maintain with the help of thermostate at specified temperature $37\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The schedule time intervals, the freshed medium were is added. The sample were assayed by UV spectrophotometer by measuring absorbance at 405 nm and 0.1 N HCl is used as blank. total amount of released benzocaine were calculated from the standard graph.

Drug content:

Five tablets were crushed, powdered and the blended equivalent to 250 mg of benzocaine was weighed and dissolved in suitable quantity of solvent (water). The solution was filtered with the help of filter and suitably diluted and drug content was analysed by UV spectrophotometrically at (405 nm) . Each sample was analysed in triplicates regression were found to be 0.92.

Fig 1 :Calibration curve for benzocaine.

Table No.-3.

Sr.No.	Concentration	Absorbance
1	10	0.01
2	20	0.03
3	30	0.05
4	40	0.07
5	50	0.08
6	60	0.089
7	70	0.95

Table 2 : Evaluation parameters with variable binder concentration.

Sr.no.	Parameters	20% binder Concentration	30% binder concentration	40% binder concentration
1	Bulk density	0.2768	0.283	0.2714
2	Tapped density	0.3295	0.3269	0.3304
3	Carr's index	15.99	13.42	17.85
4	Hausner ratio	1.19	1.16	1.21
5	Angle of repose	24.5°	30.06°	20.45°
6	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	5.0	5.2	5.5
7	Friability test (%)	0.2	0.13	0.10
8	Drug release	88.5 %	88.8 %	88.3 %
9	Dissolution time	20.3	81.02	130.3
10	Assay (%)	99.05	99.05	99.05

Fig: Evaluation of granules.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

All the prepared batches of benzocaine chewable tablets were evaluated for hardness within the range. Using Monsanto hardness tester, the strength of tablets was tested. All the tablets showed good hardness. Tablets containing 20% binder concentration had minimum hardness (5.0 kg/cm²). While tablets containing 40% binder concentration had maximum hardness (5.5 kg/cm²). And 30% binder concentration had (5.2 kg/cm²) which was acceptable. The friability was less than 0.2% for all tablets and was satisfactory. Assay value of all prepared batches of benzocaine chewable tablets were within range 99.50 mg of stated amount of benzocaine. The above data obtained from evaluations and having 88.8% of drug was release for trial 30% binder concentration. While other concentration had shown 70.8% & 72.8% drug release at 30 min respectively. Variation in dissolution time cumulative % of drug dissolved in 30 min is 81.2% of benzocaine tablet.

CONCLUSION

All the benzocaine chewable tablets showed satisfactory results and all evaluations were within range with respect to hardness, friability, assay and in vitro dissolution studies. The tablet prepared with 30% binder concentration had better dissolution rate than tablet prepared with 20% and 40% respectively.

FUTURE ASPECTS

The present formulation of chewable tablet of benzocaine will be formulated as fixed dose combination with antibacterial agent which can be used in the treatment of mouth ulcer.

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